

Predicting Pochampally Handloom Silk Saree Purchase Behaviour - A Study on Indian Consumers

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Abstract:

Background: In this study, the purchase behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees (PHSS) is understood and predicted. This study explores whether Purchase Intention mediates Consumer Satisfaction to predict Purchase Behaviour. Further Association with Handloom Products is a moderator to understanding the relation between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees. This paper empirically examines the impact of purchase intention on Purchase Behaviour with one product i.e., Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees.

Methods: The data was collected from 412 respondents (consumers of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees) from February 2022 to April 2022 through an online survey method. An empirical examination was conducted using the WarpPLS method.

Results & Conclusion: The analysis of data with WarpPLS reveals a significant relation among the variables is consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of the consumer. It confirms that, the mediating effect of Purchase Intention in the association among Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of consumers. It is found that the role of moderator, i.e., Association with Handloom Silk Sarees has a negative impact on Purchase Behaviour.

Keywords: Association with Handloom Products, Consumer Satisfaction, Purchase Behaviour, Purchase Intention, and WarpPLS

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1. Introduction

The Handloom industry is facing the challenge of sustainability in the market due to tough competition from power looms. Another reason could be its failure to attract the consumers and retain them.

The prior literature talks about the studies related to consumer satisfaction, consumer perception, consumer attitudes, and so on for the purchase of handloom products. These articles mostly cover the consumer antecedents, purchase intentions, consumer attitudes, and consumer satisfaction towards handloom products [1, 2, 3, 4]

Less attention was paid and little work was done on empirical studies that looked into the Purchase Behaviour of handloom products especially, Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees, which is a niche handloom product.

1.1 Research questions of the study

The questions of this research are to test (i) Whether Consumer Satisfaction directly influences the Purchase Intention towards Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees, (ii) Whether Consumer Satisfaction directly influences the Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees, (iii) Is purchase Intention directly influence the Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees? (iv) Does Purchase Intention mediate the relation among Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of consumers of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees? (v) Whether Association with Handloom Products moderates the strength/ direction between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees.

2. Materials & Methods

The study population comprised Indian Handloom consumers who purchased Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees at least once. The sample size for the current study was chosen using the statistical tool G*Power analysis, with certain assumptions like 0.15 as effect size and 3 predictors. The study required a sample size of 119, but data were gathered from 412 participants by mailing the structured questionnaire to 526 participants.

The study was conducted using the *snowball sampling method* [5] which is a non-probability sampling technique. The survey was conducted online. The primary data was gathered using the Survey approach. A total of 27 items comprised demographical data (10 items) and 17 items for measuring the latent variables. They are **Consumer Satisfaction (7 items); Purchase Intension (6 items) Purchase Behaviour (4 items) and Association with Handloom Products (1 item)**. Five-point Likert scale, with a scale of “1- Strongly Disagree to 5- Strongly Agree” was used to assess the replies.

3. Results & Discussion

Initially, descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, and correlations were calculated using IBM SPSS 27. The normality of data was examined by the kurtosis and skewness values of the variables which are presented in Table 1. The values of descriptive statistics (Table 1) indicate a moderate degree of correlation among the study variables. A high correlation is observed between purchase intention and Consumer Satisfaction.

Table 1- Descriptive statistics

Sl. No.	Latent construct	Mean	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness	CS	PI	CBB	AHP
1	CS-Consumer Satisfaction	3.35	1.13	-0.424	-0.630	1			
2	PI-Purchase Intention	3.10	1.06	-0.730	-0.267	0.680**	1		
3	CBB-Purchase Behaviour	3.89	0.67	0.386	-0.780	0.375**	0.306**	1	
4	AHP-Association with Handloom Products	2.20	1.12	-1.042	0.588	0.279**	0.244**	0.05	1

Note: (i) ** ‘correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)
(ii) ‘Author’s compilation based on the findings’.

Figure 1, illustrates the conceptual model for this study,

Figure 1- Conceptual model for the study

(NOTE: CS- Consumer Satisfaction; PI- Purchase Intention; CBB- Purchase Behaviour; AHP- Association with Handloom Products).

The data was analyzed based on the conceptual model by using WarpPLS [6] for twin objectives (i) psychometric analysis and (ii) path coefficients significance and predictive relevance.

3.1 Psychometric analysis

The questionnaire for the study was tested for Psychometric analysis i.e., Validity and Reliability and the findings are shown in (Table 2). Reliability was tested with Cronbach α statistic. The Cronbach α value of latent variables taken for the study ranges from 0.62 to 0.93, suggesting that, the reliability of the constructs is within acceptable limits.

Table 2 - Psychometrics statistics (Reliability & Validity)

Sl.no.	Latent construct	No. of items	Cronbach α values	CR	AVE	VIF	DV
1	Consumer Satisfaction	7	0.931	0.945	0.711	2.025	0.843
2	Purchase Intention	6	0.862	0.897	0.594	1.874	0.771
3	Purchase Behaviour	4	0.616	0.776	0.51	1.171	0.689
4	Association with Handloom Products	1	1	1	1	1.128	1

Note: (i) (CR- 'Composite Reliability'; AVE- 'Average Variance Extracted'; VIF- 'Variance Inflation Factor', DV – 'Discriminant Validity

(ii) ('Author's compilation based on the findings)

Convergent (CR) and Discriminant (AVE) validity methods were used to test the validity of data by using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The Fornell- Lacker criterion, 1981 was used for testing Discriminant Validity, which means, the square root of Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The present study produces adequate Discriminant Validity for the constructs that are Consumer Satisfaction (0.843), Purchase Intention (0.771), Purchase Behaviour (0.689), and Association with Handloom Products (1.000) which exceed the absolute values of the defined constructs' standard correlation square.

Partial Least Squares analysis was used to test the suggested conceptual model's compatibility with the gathered data, according to the threshold values [7] to test for Convergent validity all the items' loadings are above 0.7. The Convergent and Discriminant validity is sufficiently good in the present study.

3.2 path coefficients significance and predictive relevance

Path coefficients significance and predictive relevance were performed in two stages i) developing and testing the hypothesis and ii) evaluation of the overall model.

3.2.1 Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis H_1

Hypothesis H_1 i.e., "Consumer Satisfaction has a significant effect on Purchase Intention of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees", represents the direct path in the study. The variable relationship statistics are calculated using partial least squares, the results of the same are shown in Table 3. The table displays the calculated values of path co-efficient, R^2 and adjusted R^2 .

Table 3 - Direct Influence of Variable Customer Satisfaction on Purchase Intention

Description path	Path coefficient	R^2	Adjusted R^2	P value	Result
CS \rightarrow PI	0.70	0.483	0.482	<0.001	Significant & Supported H_1

(Note: 'Author's compilation based on the findings)

The direct influence of the Consumer satisfaction Purchase Intention of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees is significant at 0.001 levels and the path coefficient is 0.70

Hypotheses H_2 and H_3

In this section H_2 i.e., "Purchase Intention has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees" and H_3 i.e., "Consumer Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees" are tested using Partial Least Squares statistics and the results of the same are presented in (Table 4).

The two hypotheses i.e., H₂ and H₃ represent the direct paths in this study, the variable relationship statistics are tested from the value of the path coefficients and p-values, and the results are shown in Table 4:

Table 4 - Direct influence of variable CS, PI on CBB

Description path	Path coefficient	P value	Result
PI → CBB	0.163	<0.001	Significant & Supported H ₂
CS → CBB	0.336	<0.001	Significant & Supported H ₃

(Note: Author's compilation based on the findings)

The direct influence of Consumer Satisfaction on the Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees is significant at 0.001 levels and the path coefficient is 0.336. Purchase Intention influences the Purchase Behaviour of consumers of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees is significant at 0.001 level and the path coefficient is 0.163

Hypothesis H₄

To test H₄ i.e., the moderation effect of Association with Handloom Products between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour, presented in Table 5.

Table 5 - Moderation Effect of Association with Handloom Products between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour

Description path	Path coefficient	R ²	Adjusted R ²	P value	Result
AHP*CS → CBB	-0.17	0.26	0.25	<0.001	Significant

(Note: Author's compilation based on the results)

The moderation effect of Association with Handloom Products shows the negative impact with the path coefficient i.e., -0.17 and p < 0.001. This is indicating that there is a significant impact of the moderator on the relationship between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour but the direction is negative.

Hypothesis H₅

Hypothesis H₅ "Purchase Intention Mediates the Effect of Consumer Satisfaction on Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees", is formulated. The researcher wants to examine the combined impact of Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Intention of the consumer on Purchase Behaviour. To check the role of a mediator, Variance Accounted for (VAF) method [8] is used in this study. VAF is calculated as indirect effect/ Total effect. The values of the VAF for mediation analysis are shown in Table 6.

Table 6 - Effect of Mediator PI on CBB

Description of the effects	Path Coefficient
Indirect effect of the path	0.113
Direct effect of the path	0.336
Total effect of the path	0.450
VAF (indirect effect/total effect)	0.251

(NOTE: Author's compilation based on the findings)

The VAF (indirect effect/ Total effect) value is 0.251 or 25.1%. The range of this value is between 20 % and 80 %, meaning that there is partial mediation [8]; thus, it indicates that Purchase Intention has a partial mediation effect among the constructs of Consumer Satisfaction on Purchase Behaviour of the consumer. These findings reveal that Purchase Behaviour is not only influenced by Consumer Satisfaction but also by Purchase Intention, which mediates Purchase Behaviour.

3.2.2 Overall model evaluation:

The evaluation of the model is done using the Goodness-of-Fit (GoF). This is expressed in terms of Average path coefficient (APC), Average adjusted R-squared (AARS), Average full Collinearity VIF (AFVIF), Tenenhaus GoF (GoF), Sympton's paradox ratio (SPR) and the findings are displayed in Table 7.

Table 7 - Overall Conceptual Model Evaluation indices

Description	Model statistics	Decision
Average Path Coefficient	0.340 (p<0.001)	Accept
Average R-Squared	0.372 (p<0.001)	Accept
Average Adjusted R-Squared	0.369 (p<0.001)	Accept
Average block Variance Inflation Factor	1.260 (<=3.3)	Accept
Average Full Collinearity VIF	1.458 (<=3.3)	Accept
Tenenhaus Goodness of Fit	0.531 (>=0.36)	Accept
Sympson's Paradox Ratio	1 (accept if it is =1)	Accept
R-Squared Contribution Ratio	1 (accept if it is =1)	Accept
Statistical Suppression Ratio	1 (accept if it is >=0.7)	Accept

According to the findings in Table 7, all evaluation indices can be accepted since they meet the standards of all Goodness of Fit. AVIF= 1.260 <=3.3, means there is no multicollinearity problem between indicators. GoF= 0.36, means that the model is fit and very good to use for prediction. The overall resulting model with the values is shown in Figure 2

Figure 2: Resulting model with the values using WarpPLS 8.0

3.3 Influence of Consumer Satisfaction on Purchase Behaviour

As per the research results, Consumer Satisfaction had a significant effect on Purchase Behaviour. This can be seen from the values of path coefficient (0.34) and p-value (<0.001) which means that Consumer Satisfaction has a relationship of 34% with the Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees. Thus, these results indicate that increasing Consumer Satisfaction is proven to be able to make increase the Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees, so that, the alternate hypothesis (H_3) can be accepted. Purchase Behaviour has tended to focus on the cognitive (expectations, performance, and disconfirmation) rather than affective components (positive and negative effects) of satisfaction with some notable exceptions [9]. Some authors [10] stated that to keep the business going and revenue increasing, they have to keep the customers satisfied by measuring their Customers' Buying Behaviour patterns from time to time [11]. Consumer Satisfaction acts as a good predictor of purchase behaviour [12].

3.4 Influence of Purchase Intention on Purchase Behaviour

As per the research results, Purchase Intention had a significant effect on the Purchase Behaviour of consumers of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees. This can be supported by the values of path coefficient (0.16) and p-value (<0.001) that indicate Purchase Intention has a relationship of 16% with Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees, so that, the alternate hypothesis (H_2) accepted. Purchase intentions are prerequisites for people willing to adopt certain buying behaviour [13]. Researchers investigate the intention, assuming that Purchase Behaviour will automatically swing along [14].

3.5 Influence of Consumer Satisfaction on Purchase Intention

As per the research results, Consumer Satisfaction had a significant effect on Purchase Intention. This can be supported by the values of path coefficient (0.70) and p-value (<0.001) that indicates Consumer Satisfaction has a relationship of 70% with Purchase Intention towards Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees, so that, the alternate hypothesis (H_1) can be accepted. The study of the consumer judgment process i.e., satisfaction levels is important

for understanding consumer purchase intention discovered that customer purchase intention is significantly related to customer satisfaction and perceived product quality.

3.6 Mediating Role of Purchase Intention between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of Consumers of PHSS

As per the research results, the mediating role of Purchase Intention had a significant impact on Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of consumers of PHSS. This can be supported by the values of path coefficient (0.45) and p-value (<0.001) indicating that with the mediation of Purchase Intention, Consumer Satisfaction has a relationship of 45% with the Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees, so that the alternate hypothesis (H_5) can be accepted. Purchase Intention is one of the important factors in predicting the Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees [15].

3.7 Moderating Role of Association with Handloom Products on Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour

Based on the results from the research, the moderating effect of Association with Handloom Products had a negative and significant effect on the relationship between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour. This can be supported by the values of $\beta = -0.165$ and p-value (<0.001) which indicates that the moderation of Association with Handloom Products on the relation between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of consumers of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees has a 16% relationship, so that, the alternate hypothesis (H_4) can be accepted.

4. Conclusions

The present study identified that there is a negative moderation observed by the Association with Handloom Products between Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees. The consumers were satisfied with the attributes like designs, durability, comfort, quality, price, and availability which in turn led to the Purchase Behaviour of the consumer of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees. Consumer Satisfaction with Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees had mediated by the Purchase Intention of Purchase Behaviour. But there is a negative impact of Association with Handloom Products in relation to Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Behaviour. The study, therefore, suggests that weavers, master weavers, and marketers should concentrate on the attributes of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees rather than their association with the selected product. They want to plan the marketing mix strategies to change the negative relation to positive relation with association towards Purchase Behaviour of Pochampally Handloom Silk Sarees.

This study has some limitations also, the sample size of 412, which cannot be considered a large sample, and the inclusion of selected predictors; therefore, there is future scope for researchers to study more predictors of Purchase Behaviour such as consumer awareness, consumer loyalty, brand perception and so on, the study is that cross-sectional nature, in future research; longitudinal study designs can be used to evaluate the proposed model to increase its acceptability. Future studies can get motivated to extend the proposed research model by considering the limitations of this study.

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